

THE EFFECT OF ALGEBRA TILES IN THE OPERATIONS OF INTEGERS AND POLYNOMIALS TO THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 7 STUDENTS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 30

Issue 9

Pages: 1442-1452

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2924

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14652507

Manuscript Accepted: 12-27-2024

The Effect of Algebra Tiles in the Operations of Integers and Polynomials to the Academic Performance of Grade 7 Students

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Abstract

The study determined the effects of algebra tiles in the operations of integers and polynomials to the academic performance of Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension enrolled in the academic year 2023-2024. A standardized questionnaire based on the Enhanced Regional Unified Numeracy Test (ERUNT) of DepEd Region VI for the operations on integers and based on the self-learning modules published by the Schools Division of Pasig City for the operations of polynomials were used in gathering the data. There are 80 participants in determining the pre-test and post-test performance of the Grade 7 students. Out of 80 participants, 40 were assigned as control group. In the operations of integers, the pre-test mean is 20.20, while the post-test mean is 26.38. In the operations of polynomials, the pre-test mean is 2.40, while the post-test mean is 7.83. The results revealed that there was an increase in the performance of the control group. There are also 40 participants in the experimental group who took the pre-test and post-test in the operations of integers, the pre-test mean is 19.17, interpreted as nearly proficient, while post-test mean is 27.78, interpreted as nearly proficient. In the operations of polynomials, the pre-test mean is 2.37, interpreted as not proficient, while the post-test mean is 9.70, interpreted as low proficient. Thus, there is an increase in the performance of the experimental group in the operations of integers and polynomials. Using the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test at 0.05 level of significance in the operations of integers, the computed value is -5.518 and the p-value is <0.001. In the operations of polynomials, the computed value is -5.519 and the p-value is 0.001. Since the P value in both operations are less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group in the operation of integers and polynomials. The result suggests that algebra tiles are effective in improving students' performance in the operation of integers and polynomials. This implies that the class sessions and the use of algebra tiles has a significant effect to the performance of the Grade 7 students. Furthermore, there is no significant difference between the control and experimental group in the operations of integers and polynomials.

Keywords: *algebra, integers, polynomials, academic performance*

Introduction

The significance of mathematics as a fundamental skill set cannot be overstated, as it underpins various academic disciplines and real-world applications. However, despite its importance, numerous learners struggle to grasp mathematical concepts due to the abstract nature of the subject matter and weak foundation in basic mathematics. According to research, learners struggle to solve simple problems involving operations on integers, particularly when addition and subtraction are involved (Khalid et al., 2018). Students were taught to follow rules and procedures abstractly without going through the models for better conceptual understanding (Khalid and Embong, 2020).

Consequently, educators continually seek innovative pedagogical approaches to facilitate deeper understanding and engagement with mathematical concepts. One such method gaining traction is the integration of concrete manipulatives, such as algebra tiles, into the instructional framework. These tangible resources serve as tangible representations of abstract mathematical ideas, offering students a hands-on, interactive approach to learning. The study found that using algebra tiles helped students learn basic algebraic concepts (Bartolini & Martignone, 2020).

According to Jaisi (2020), algebra tiles are a type of mathematical manipulative that helps students comprehend algebraic thought processes and concepts more fully. It has been demonstrated that these tiles offer concrete examples for beginning algebra students in elementary, middle, high school, and college. These are a hands-on manipulative that can represent and solve integers and algebraic expressions. It can be used to teach and learn various algebraic concepts, including the operations of integers and polynomials. For example, to add or subtract integers using algebra tiles, students can simply combine or separate the tiles that represent the integers. To multiply polynomials using algebra tiles, students can arrange the tiles to represent the product of the two polynomials.

As observed from other schools, algebra tiles was found effective. Thus, it motivated the researcher to conduct the study. The researcher sought to determine the effect of algebra tiles in the operations of integers and polynomials to the performance of Grade 7 students.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to determine the effects of algebra tiles in the operations of integers and polynomials to the academic performance of Grade 7 students. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the pre-test and post-test performance of the control group of the Grade 7 students in the operations of integers and

- polynomials?
2. What is the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group of the Grade 7 students in the operations of integers and polynomials?
 3. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group of the Grade 7 students in the operations of integers and polynomials?
 4. Is there a significant difference between the post-test performance of the control group and the experimental group of the Grade 7 students in the operations of integers and polynomials?

Methodology

Research Design

This research aimed to determine the effects of algebra tiles in the operations of integers and polynomials on the Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension.

In the study, a pretest- posttest control group design was employed. The experimental group and the control group make up this experimental design. The two groups were expected to be comparable and equivalent. The simplest experimental design tests just one treatment that is compared with a no-treatment condition. Subjects or participants are assigned to either be the treatment or control (no-treatment) group and are measured or tested both before and after the experimental treatment is implemented (Valencia, 2023).

Participants

The participants of the study were the Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension in the Schools Division of Sipalay City who were officially enrolled in the academic year 2023-2024.

Population and Sample Size

The participants of the study were the Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension. Three existing classes from the same level at the said school were taken. Twenty-six (26) students from section Ruby, twenty-six (26) students from section Pearl, and twenty-eight (28) students from section Emerald, a total of Eighty (80) students.

Sampling Technique

In determining the number of respondents, random sampling was used. Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension was chosen among the schools in the Schools Division of Sipalay City.

Since three (3) existing classes were taken as respondents of the study, each class was divided into two. The first thirteen students for each section in Grade 7 Ruby and section Pearl respectively were grouped as experimental groups and the remaining thirteen were grouped as control groups. For section Emerald, the first fourteen students were grouped as experimental group and the remaining fourteen were grouped as control group. The samples were grouped concerning academic performance, sex, and time.

For the consideration of academic performance, high-performing students and low-performing students based on their 1st quarter academic performance were divided equally for each group to uphold fairness in the conduct of the study.

For sex, the number of male and female members for the control and experimental group in the section with an odd number of students was almost equal. And, equal distribution of participants for the sections with an even number of male and female students.

For the time, the three chosen sections have morning schedules for their mathematics class. The first section’s schedule was from 7:30 to 8:30, the second section was from 8:30 to 9:30, and the third section was from 10:45 to 11:45.

Distribution of Participants

The researcher considers the academic performance and sex in determining the participants for the control and experimental group to avoid bias.

Academic Performance

The table below shows the difference between the first quarter academic performance of the control group and the experimental group in mathematics.

Table 1. *Difference between the First Quarter Academic Performance the Control Group and Experimental Group in Mathematics*

Polynomial	n	Mean	Std. Deviation
Control Group	40	83.425	27.456
Experimental Group	40	83.325	31.174

Computed Value (Z): -0.083
 Tabular Value : -1.645
 Decision : Accept Ho
 Interpretation : not significant at a 0.05 level of significance

The average grade of the experimental group is 83.325 with a standard deviation of 31.174, while the control group is 83.425 with a standard deviation of 27.456. Using the z-test for two sample means at a 0.05 level of significance, the computed value is -0.083, and the tabular value is -1.645. Since the absolute computed value is less than the absolute tabular value, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between the academic performance of the control group and the experimental group.

Sex

The table below shows the distribution of participants in the control and experimental group in terms of sex.

Table 2. Distribution of Participants according to Sex

Section	Enrolment		Experimental		Control		Total
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	
1	13	13	7	6	6	7	26
2	14	12	7	6	7	6	26
3	16	12	8	6	8	6	28
Total	43	37	22	18	21	19	80

Out of 80 participants, 40 were grouped as control and 40 were grouped as experimental. For the experimental group with 40 participants, 22 are male and 18 are female. For the control group with 40 participants, 21 are male and 19 are female. The uneven number of participants for each sex in the groups is caused by the odd number of male and female students in section 1.

Instrument

The standardized Questionnaire adapted from the Enhanced Regional Unified Numeracy Test (ERUNT) of DepEd Region VI for the operations on integers and a standardized questionnaire for the operations on polynomials from the self-learning modules published by the Schools Division of Pasig City was used in gathering the data. The questionnaire was composed of two parts. Part I was the operations on integers and Part II was the operations on polynomials. Part I was composed of 10 items of addition, 10 items of subtraction, 10 items of multiplication, and 10 items of division. Part II was composed of 5 items of addition, 5 items of subtraction, 5 items of multiplication, and 5 items of division. Student's scores were then categorized as highly proficient, proficient, nearly proficient, low proficient, and not proficient based on the percentage of correct answers. Highly proficient for 90%-100%, proficient for 75%-89%, nearly proficient for 50%-74%, low proficient for 25-49%, and not proficient for 0%-24%.

Procedure

To gather the data, a letter was written and sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Schools Division of Sinalay City (see appendix D.1), Public Schools District Supervisor of Cluster 8 (see appendix D.2), where the school of the participants belongs, and School Head of Gil Montilla National High School (see appendix D.3), that the researcher conducted a study.

Experimental Procedures

Pre-intervention Phase: right after determining the group of participants, the researcher conducted a pre-test on two different groups: the control, and the experimental group to check their knowledge about the operations on integers and polynomials. Right before the test, the researcher allowed the participants to sit on the seats they were comfortable with and ensured that the ventilation, lighting, and surroundings were conducive to learning. And, as they were seated on the seats they freely chose, a pre-test was administered.

Intervention Phase: the researcher conducted class sessions for four weeks in two different groups on the operations of integers and polynomials: the control group received the traditional approach or without the use of algebra tiles; the experimental group on the other hand received the treatment or used algebra tiles.

The table below shows the competencies covered for the operations of integers and polynomials and the activity log for four (4) weeks of research or implementation period.

Table 3. Competencies and Activity Log for 4 Weeks of Research Period

Day	Competencies	Activity Log
1-5 (Week 1)	Represents the Absolute value of a number on a number line as a distance of a number from 0. Performs Fundamental Operations on Integers.	The teacher taught the students to represent the absolute value of a number on a number line. Students were also given corresponding activities to promote mastery. The experimental group and control group were given similar instructions and activities on the operations of integers. They only differ in the approaches to solving such operations. The experimental group was taught to perform the operations on integers using algebra tiles, while the control group used the traditional way of solving such operations.
6-9 (Week 2)	Illustrates and differentiates related terms in Algebra: a. a where n is a positive integer. b. Constants and variables c. Literal Coefficients and Numerical	The teacher discussed all the important concepts in algebra. Students were given group activities to determine the constants and variables in each of the expressions. They were also given time to present their work in the class. The teacher assigned individual activities in determining the literal coefficient and numerical coefficient for each of the terms in an expression.

	Coefficients	The teacher let the students explore and share with the class the meaning of algebraic expressions and count the terms of the given polynomial.
	d. Algebraic Expressions, terms, and polynomials.	The teacher introduced the algebra tiles and their corresponding value to the experimental group.
	e. Number of terms, degree of the term, and degree of the polynomial.	
10-13 (Week 3)	Add and Subtract Polynomials.	The teacher gave activities on the addition and subtraction of polynomials. The experimental group was tasked to perform the operations of polynomials using algebra tiles, while the control group was tasked to perform the said operation using the traditional way.
		The teacher gave individual activities to enhance the skills in the operations of polynomials.
14-17 (Week 4)	Derives the laws of the exponent.	The teacher gave activities in multiplying polynomials. Students were given activities in dividing polynomials.
	Multiplies and divides polynomials.	The experimental group was tasked to perform the operations of polynomials using algebra tiles, while the control group was tasked to perform the said operation using the traditional way.
		The teacher gave individual activities to enhance the skills in the operations of polynomials.

Post-intervention Phase: After the sessions, the researcher conducted a post-test to check the difference between the performances of the control group and experimental group and the effects of algebra tiles in the operations on integers and polynomials. The participants freely chose the seats with the ventilation, lighting, and surroundings conducive to learning.

Upon the retrieval of the questionnaires, the data were tallied, analyzed, and tabulated. The data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Data Analysis

The data obtained in this study were subjected to appropriate descriptive and inferential statistical procedures.

In the analysis and interpretation of data, different statistical tools were used.

To answer the statement of problem number 1 which states, what is the pre-test and post-test performance of the control group in the operation of integers and polynomials, mean was used.

To answer the statement of problem number 2 which states, what is the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group in the operation of integers and polynomials, mean was used.

To answer the statement of problem number 3 which states, is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group in the operation of integers and polynomials, the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test was used.

To answer the statement of problem number 4 which states whether is there a significant difference between the post-test performance of the controlled group and experimental group in the operation of integers and polynomials, the Mann-Whitney Test was used.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered for this study.

Pre-test and Post-test Performance of the Control Group in the Operations of Integers

The table below presents the pre-test and post-test performance of the control group in the operations of integers of the Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension.

Table 4.1. *Pre-test and Post-test Performance of Control Group in the Operation of Integers*

<i>Integers</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Pre-Test	40	20.20	Nearly Proficient
Post-Test	40	26.38	Nearly Proficient

The table shows that out of 80 participants, 40 were assigned as control group. The pre-test mean of the control group in the operations of integers is 20.20, interpreted as nearly proficient, while the post-test mean is 26.38, interpreted as nearly proficient. Though the verbal interpretation of the pre-test and post-test means are both nearly proficient, the mean of the post-test scores is still higher than the mean of the pre-test scores. Thus there is an increase in the performance of the control group in the operations of integers.

The low result in the pre-test is in conformity with the study of Khalid et al. (2018) which states that students have difficulties in solving basic problems involving operations on integers, especially when it involves addition and subtraction. One of the causes mentioned by Khalid and Embong (2020) is due to students being taught to follow rules and procedures in a very abstract manner without going through the models for better conceptual understanding.

Pre-test and Post-test Performance of the Control Group in the Operations of Polynomials

The table below presents the pre-test and post-test performance of the control group in the operations of polynomials of the Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension.

Table 4.2. *Pre-test and Post-test Performance of Control Group in the Operation of Polynomials*

<i>Polynomial</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Pre-Test	40	2.40	Not Proficient
Post-Test	40	7.83	Low Proficient

The table shows that out of 80 participants, 40 were assigned as control group. The mean of the pre-test scores of the control group in the operations of polynomials is 2.40 which is interpreted as not proficient, while the mean of the post-test scores is 7.83 which is interpreted as low proficient. The means and verbal interpretation of the pre-test and post-test scores imply that there is an increase in the performance of the control group in the operations of polynomials.

The low performance in the operations of polynomials is in conformity with the Rodrigo and Alave (2021) study, which discovered that ninth-grade students at a certain public high school have poor academic achievement. Higher level arithmetic knowledge requires an understanding of the fundamentals. Even though the K–12 curriculum has been modified to spiral learning, where important topics are reviewed at each level to aid in mastery, they do not acquire the abilities necessary for middle school. Students master the fundamentals using the spiral curriculum before moving on to more complicated models. The poor pass rate of students in the first quartile of algebra was caused by the concept of distant education during the Covid 2019 epidemic, where students only learn with the help of the weekly printed modules that their teachers provide for their teachers. The Department of Education's core competencies are difficult for pupils to understand since they lack background information and do not receive direction from an instructor who should be teaching them new material. According to the study's findings, algebra teachers should ensure that their students' fluency—particularly in fundamental concepts—is developed to link algebra scores to interactive, student-centered instruction (Valencia, 2023).

Pre-test and Post-test Performance of the Experimental Group in the Operations of Integers

The table on the next page shows the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group in the operations of integers of the Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension.

Table 5.1. *Pre-test and Post-test Performance of the Experimental Group in the Operation of Integers*

<i>Integers</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Pre-Test	40	19.17	Nearly Proficient
Post-Test	40	27.78	Nearly Proficient

The table shows that out of 40 participants of experimental group who took the pre-test in the operations of integers the mean is 19.17, interpreted as nearly proficient, while in the post-test, the mean is 27.78, interpreted as nearly proficient. Though the verbal interpretations of the pre-test and post-test are similar, the post-test mean is higher than the pre-test mean. Thus, there is an increase in the performance of the experimental group in the operations of integers.

Students' low performance in pre-test and an increase in post-test is reflected in the study of Khalid and Embong (2020) which states that students find understanding integers and solving problems involving operations on integers difficult and challenging. It is common knowledge among educators that multiplying two negative numbers will get a positive response, but adding two negative numbers will yield a negative one. The fact that pupils do not use the multiplication of negative integers in their daily lives makes it harder for them to understand. Nonetheless, they must grasp the fundamental algebraic operations of adding, subtracting, multiplying, and dividing integers. There are several approaches to teach students about integer operations. Using tangible representation in conjunction with a few other representations inside a single teaching and learning process is one of the ways. Algebra tiles are useful tools because they help pupils tangibly understand mathematical concepts.

Pre-test and Post-test Performance of the Experimental Group in the Operations of Polynomials

The table below presents the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group in the operations of integers and polynomials of the Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension

Table 5.2. *Pre-test and Post-test Performance of Experimental Group in the Operation of Polynomials*

<i>Polynomial</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Pre-Test	40	2.38	Not Proficient
Post-Test	40	9.70	Nearly Proficient

The table shows that out of 40 participants of the experimental group who took the pre-test in the operations of polynomials, the mean is 2.37, interpreted as not proficient, while the post-test, the mean is 9.70, interpreted as low proficient. Since the mean of the post-test

is higher than the mean of the pretest and the verbal interpretation is nearly proficient and low proficient respectively. There is an increase in the performance of the experimental group in the operations of polynomials.

The increase in students' performance in the operation of polynomials with the aid of algebra tiles is supported by the study of Moore & Rimbe (2021), in which they claimed that algebra tiles aid pupils in modeling mathematical concepts in math and related subjects. Students can solve problems more intuitively and understand the quantities we are working with using algebraic tiles. According to Caylan (2018), algebra tiles help pupils comprehend that the concept of a variable is arbitrary.

Difference between the Pre-test and Post-test Performance of the Experimental Group in the Operations of Integers

The table below shows the difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group in the operations of integers of the Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension.

Table 6.1. Difference between the Pre-test and Post-test Performance of the Experimental Group in the Operation of Integers

<i>Pre-test and Post-test Scores in the Operation of Integers</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Negative Ranks	0	0.00
Positive Ranks	40	20.50
Total	40	

Computed value (Z) : -5.518
P-value : <0.001
Decision : Reject H_0
Interpretation : Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 6.1 reveals the difference between the post-test and pre-test scores in the operations of integers. The frequency of the negative ranks between the post-test and pre-test scores or the result where the post-test score is less than the pre-test score of the experimental group is 0 with the mean rank of 0, while the frequency of positive ranks between the post-test and pre-test scores or the result where post-test is greater than the pre-test is 40 with the mean rank of 20.50.

Using the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test at 0.05 level of significance, the computed value is -5.518 and the p-value is <0.001. Since the P value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group in the operation of integers. The result suggests that algebra tiles are effective in improving students' performance in the operation of integers.

The finding conforms with the study of Khalid and Embong (2020) in which they found that students actively employed algebra tiles as a tool to solve problems in the classroom when they were given them as a manipulative for learning numbers. They manipulate the tiles and acquire confidence. When students connect what they have learned from one representation to another, learning eventually occurs. By actively participating, they could apply critical and creative thinking skills and establish connections between the various representations. Since the teacher fosters a collaborative environment, students feel more confident and can tackle many issues that are presented. This is mostly because they can see and work with the item (algebra tiles) that has been provided to them.

Difference between the Pre-test and Post-test Performance of the Experimental Group in the Operations of Polynomials

The table below shows the difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group in the operations of polynomials of the Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension.

Table 6.2. Difference between the Pre-test and Post-test Performance of the Experimental Group in the Operations of Polynomials

<i>Pretest and Posttest Scores in the Operation of Polynomials</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Negative Ranks	0	0.00
Positive Ranks	40	20.50
Total	40	

Computed value (Z) : -5.519
P-value : <0.001
Decision : Reject H_0
Interpretation : Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on Table 6.2, the number of negative ranks between the post-test and pre-test scores or the result where the post-test score is less than the pre-test score of the experimental group is 0 with the mean rank of 0, while the frequency of positive ranks between the post-test and pre-test scores or the result where post-test is greater than the pre-test is 40 with the mean rank of 20.50.

Using the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test at 0.05 level of significance, the computed value is -5.519 and the p-value is 0.001. Since the P value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group in the operations of polynomials. Hence, the result implies that algebra tiles improve the performance of Grade 7 students in the operation of polynomials.

The result is in conformity with the study by Caylan (2018) in which he found that teaching algebraic concepts of zero and operations with integers and polynomials to children in the 7th, 8th, and 9th grades was significantly impacted using algebra tiles. Students can

move between physical and symbolic representations of the concepts with the use of algebra tiles. Students can investigate algebraic expressions visually and practically with algebra tiles, and they can also learn the rules by applying them to their own experiences. Additionally, modeling using algebra tiles helps pupils develop their conceptual understanding and visualization abilities.

Difference between the Post-Test Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Operations of Integers

The table below shows the difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group in the operations of integers of the Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension.

Table 7.1. *Difference between the Post-test Performance of Control Group and Experimental Group in the Operations of Integers*

<i>Integers</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Control Group	40	38.41
Experimental Group	40	42.59

Computed value (Z) : 716.50
P-value : 0.421
Decision : Accept Ho
Interpretation : Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 7.1 reveals the difference between the post-test performance of the control group and the experimental group in the operations of integers. The number of participants for the control group who took the post-test is equal to the number of participants for the experimental group. The mean rank of the control group is 38.41, while the mean rank of the experimental group is 42.59.

Using the Mann-Whitney Test at a 0.05 level of significance, the computed value (U) is 716.50 and the p-value is 0.421. Since the P-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between the post-test performance of the control group and the experimental group in the operations of integers.

The implication is contrary to the study of Khalid and Embong (2020) which states that algebra tiles are effective manipulatives because they enable students to make sense of mathematical problems concretely. Its uses include the application to addition, subtraction, multiplication and division of integers; to complete the square; to factor expressions and to relay the distributive property. Algebra tiles are the visual and hands-on way for students to explore algebraic expressions, where students can learn from their own experiences. Thus, it is more meaningful compared to other models such as the number-line representation, which is less effective in solving problems related to multiplication and division of integers.

Difference between the Post-Test Performance of the Control and Experimental Group in the Operations of Polynomials

The table below shows the difference between the pre-test and post-test performance of the experimental group in the operations of polynomials of the Grade 7 students of Gil Montilla National High School- Camindangan Extension.

Table 7.2. *Difference between the post-test performance of the control group and experimental group in the operations of polynomials*

<i>Polynomial</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean Rank</i>
Control Group	40	35.90
Experimental Group	40	45.10

Computed value (Z) : 616.00
P-value : 0.075
Decision : Accept Ho
Interpretation : Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table presents the difference between the post-test performance of the control group and the experimental group in the operations of polynomials. There is an equal number of participants for the control group and the experimental group who took the post-test. The control group obtained a mean rank of 35.90, while the experimental group obtained a mean rank of 45.10.

Using the Mann-Whitney Test at a 0.05 level of significance, the computed value (U) is 616.00 and the p-value is 0.075 at a 0.05 level of significance. Since the P-value is greater than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The implication is contrary to the study of Ergene and Haser (2021) which claims that using algebraic tiles widely increased student performance. Employing algebra tiles to teach and understand the subject has shown to be a very successful and promising approach that also helps students become better problem solvers. Valencia (2023) states that algebra tiles are important resources for the pedagogical and subject knowledge growth of aspiring mathematics instructors since they provide a realistic approach to teaching factorization and multiplication of polynomials". However, there are drawbacks to utilizing algebra tiles as teaching aids. The different units that arise from the usage of algebraic tiles must be thoroughly understood by teachers.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this research study, the conclusions that were arrived are as follows:

The performance of the control group of Grade 7 students in the operations of integers and polynomials has increased.

The performance of the experimental group of Grade 7 students has improved as seen in the mean gaps between the post-test and pre-test.

The intervention has a significant effect in the performance of experimental group in the operations of integers and polynomials. Hence, the class sessions and the manipulative used which is the algebra tiles are effective.

Statistically, the post-test performance of the control group and the experimental group of Grade 7 students in the operations of integers and polynomials has no significant difference.

Considering the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are made:

Students can be regularly given activities and drills that will further enhance their skills and understanding of the operations of integers and polynomials. Teachers may introduce algebra tiles as a manipulative to the learners.

It is highly recommended that the school together with the Schools Division of Sipalay City will plan and craft a more improved approaches and strategies that will elevate the skills of the learners in the integer and polynomial operations for this will serve as their foundation in learning abstract concepts in mathematics. They can also think of effective methods, strategies, and materials to make students learn basic algebra and other mathematics concepts better. Teachers can be equipped with the strategies of using algebra tiles in the operation of integers and polynomials.

Teachers can approach teaching as an interactive process where students build new mathematical ideas and make connections to their everyday lives through practical experiences. To help students gain a deeper knowledge of the subject, math teachers can utilize algebra tiles to help them translate abstract facts into observable and logical comprehension using manipulatives and images.

For future researchers, it is recommended to conduct further studies on the use and effects of algebra tiles especially in algebraic understanding including other variables and skills not mentioned in the current study. More interviews or narratives with teachers and students may be a part of future research to learn more about the perspectives of both parties on the usage of manipulatives like algebra tiles to help students understand mathematics conceptually.

References

- Admin (2023). *Mathematical Reasoning (Definition, Statements, and Types)*. BYJUS. <https://byjus.com/maths/statements-in-mathematical-reasoning/#:~:text=What%20is%20Mathematical%20Reasoning%3F,easy%20and%20fun%20to%20solve>.
- Akpalu, R., Adaboh, S., & Boateng, S. S. (2018). Towards improving senior high school students' conceptual understanding of the system of two linear equations. *International Journal of Educational Research Review*, 3(1), 28-40.
- Almond, N. (2022). *Fluency, Reasoning, and Problem-Solving: What This Looks Like In Every Maths Lesson*. <https://thirdspacelearning.com/>
- Asparin, A. A. & Tan, D. A. (2018). Students' Problem-Solving Skills in Enhanced Gradual Release of Responsibility Instruction Model. *Asian Academic Research Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 5(3), 121-128.
- Bartolini, M. G., & Martignone, F. (2020). Manipulatives in mathematics education. *Encyclopedia of Mathematics Education*, 487-494. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-15789-0_93
- Basilio, K. D., Asanon, F. J., Sahidena, R. A., Abdul, A. J., Espacio, L.-G. P., & Alviar, J. V. (2022). Ready or not ready: Extent of readiness in mathematics of grade 7 students. *International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR)*, 6(8), 81-85.
- Bulos, F. B. (2021). *Mathematics Vocabulary and Mathematical Ability of Grade 7 Students*.
- Busalim, A. H., Masrom, M., Normeza, W., & Wan, B. (2019). The impact of Facebook addiction and self-esteem on students' academic performance: A multi-group analysis. *Computers&Education*, 142(August), 103651. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2019.103651>.
- Capuno, R., Necesario, R., Etcuban, J. O., Espina, R., Padillo, G., & Manguilimotan, R. (2019). Attitudes, Study Habits, and Academic Performance of Junior High School Students in Mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 14(3), 547-561. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/5768>
- Caylan, B. (2018). The effects of using algebra tiles on sixth-grade students' algebra achievement, algebraic thinking, and views about using algebra tiles.
- Cetin, H. (2019). Explaining the concept and operations of integers in primary school mathematics teaching: Opposite moel sample. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 365-370. doi:10.13189
- Ciubal-Fulgencio, N., & Tan, D. (2018). Effects of mathematics communication strategies on attitude and performance of grade 8 students, *Asian Academic Research Journal of Multi-disciplinary*, Volume 5, Issue 2, February 2018.

- Coronel, C. & Tan, D.A. (2019). Twenty-First (21st) Century Skills and Student Mathematics Performance in Self-Blend Approach, *International Journal of English, and Education*, 8(2), 342-357
- Cresswell, C., & Speelman, C. P. (2020). Does mathematics training lead to better logical thinking and reasoning? A cross-sectional assessment from students to professors. *PloS one*, 15(7), e0236153.
- Dagoc, D., Tan, D.A. (2018). Effects of Metacognitive Scaffolding on the Mathematics Performance of Grade 6 Pupils in a Cooperative Learning Environment, *International Journal of English, and Education*, 7(4), 378-391.
- Dapitan, D.A. & Caballes, D. G. (2019). Exploratory effects of strategic intervention materials in general biology 2. *CiiT International Journal of Biometrics and Bioinformatics*, 11(3), 37-41.
- Delos Santos, K. B., Eduarte, A. R., Juaban, J. L., Abdul, R. J., Najimin, L. A., & Alviar, J. V. (2022). Effects of video tutorials on the mathematics achievement of students in modular distance learning. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications*, 5(2), 150-155.
- Department of Education. (2019). PISA 2018: National report of the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/PISA-2018Philippine-National-Report.pdf>
- DepEd (2023). Regional Memorandum No. 1092 s. 2023: Guidelines on the Utilization of the Enhance Regional Unified Numeracy Test (ERUNT) for Key Stages 2, 3, and 4.
- Dube, A., & Robinson, K. (2018). Children's understanding of multiplication and division: Insights from a pooled analysis of seven studies conducted across seven years. *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 206-219. doi:10.1111/bjdp.12217
- Ergene, B., & Haser C. (2021). Students' algebra achievement, algebraic thinking, and views in the case of using algebra tiles in groups. *Necatibey Eğitim Fakültesi Elektronik Fen ve Matematik Eğitimi Dergisi*. <https://doi.org/10.17522/balikesirnef.1019292>
- Etuban, J. O., & Pantinople, L. D. (2018). The effects of mobile application in teaching high school mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 13(3), 249-259. <https://doi.org/10.12973/iejme/3906>
- Examinations Council of Lesotho. (2018). Mathematics examiners' reports, syllabus 0178/4. Maseru: Lesotho.
- Fadillah, S., & Susiaty, U. (2019). Developing refutation text to resolve students' misconceptions in addition and subtraction of integers. *Beta: Jurnal Tadris Matematika*, 12(1)
- Fuadiah, N. F., Suryadi, D., & Turmudi. (2016). Some difficulties in understanding negative numbers faced by students a qualitative study applied at secondary schools in Indonesia. *International Education Studies*, 10(1), 24-38. doi:10.5539/ies.v10n1p24
- Garzón, J., & Bautista, J. (2018). Virtual algebra tiles: A pedagogical tool to teach and learn algebra through geometry. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 34(6), 876-883. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12296>
- Gibbs, K., & Pyman, H. (2021). Innovative teaching in a new normal. *Septentrio Conference Series*, (2). <https://doi.org/10.7557/5.5832>.
- Gopal, R., Singh, V., & Aggarwal, A. (2021). Impact of Online Classes on the Satisfaction and Performance of Students during the Pandemic period of COVID-19. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(6), 6923-6947.
- Hangdaan, R. & Maguilao S. (2020). Quarter 1- Module 10: Polynomial Equation.
- Harun, N. et al. (2023). Assessing Students' Mastery and Misconception in the Fundamental Operations on Integers. *International Journal of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics* Volume 3 Issue 3 September 2023. <https://doi.org/10.53378/353000>
- Herbert, S. (2021). Overcoming challenges in assessing mathematical reasoning. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education (Online)*, 46(8), 17-30.
- Indeed Editorial Team. (2023). Math Skills: Definition, Examples and How To Develop Them. Indeed, Career Guide. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/math-skills>
- Jaisi, R. (2020). Effectiveness of manipulative materials in teaching mathematics.
- Jamaludin, N. H., & Maat, S. M. (2020). A systematic literature review on students misconceptions in mathematics. *Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 10(6), 127-145. doi:10.6007/IJARBS/v10-i6/7273
- Khalid, M., & Embong, Z. (2019). Sources and possible causes of errors and misconceptions in operations of integers. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 15(1). doi:10.29333/iejme/6265
- Khalid, M., & Embong, Z. (2020). Sources and possible causes of errors and misconceptions in operations of integers. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 15(2), em0568.
- Khalid, M., Ibrahim, M. B., Saad, S., Othman, J., Mohd Yussuf, Y., Embong, Z., (2018, November). A preliminary study on form 1

- students errors and misconception in operations of integers. In R. Embong, H.M. Lateh (Eds) Proceeding of National Education Deans' Council Seminar (pp. 115 – 124), UNISZA, Malaysia.
- Kumar, S., Agarwal, M., & Agarwal, N. (2021). Defining and measuring the academic performance of Hei students-a critical review. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(6), 3091-3105.
- Kwakyee, D. O., Alpha, M. A., Agyei, E., Larbi, E. A., Anane, J. K., & Domonaamwin, B. C. (2022). *Complete Integers: Integers and its Applications* (Vol. 1). India: White Falcon.
- Lalian, O. (2019). The effects of using video media in mathematics Learning on students' cognitive and aspects. *AIP Conference Proceedings*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5061865>
- Lamb, L. et al. (2019). Project Z. Washington, DC: National Science Foundation award, grant number DRL-0918780
- Marpa, E. P. (2019). Common errors in algebraic expressions: A quantitative-qualitative analysis. *International Journal on Social and Education Sciences Volume*, 1(2), 63–72. ISSN: 2688-7061 (Online).
- Mcleod, S. (2023) *Constructivism Learning Theory & Educational Philosophy*. Simply Psychology
- Mejias, S., Muller, C., & Schiltz, C. (2019). Assessing mathematical school readiness. doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01173
- Moore, S. D., & Rimbey, K. (2021). *Mastering math manipulatives, grades K-3: Hands-on and virtual activities for building and connecting mathematical ideas*. Corwin Press
- Murillo, J. A. & Tan, D. A. (2019). Students' Mathematics Performance and Engagement in an Inquiry-Based Learning Approach, *International Journal of English and Education*, 8(3), 64-74, July 2019.
- Niss, M., & Højgaard, T. (2019). Mathematical competencies revisited. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 102, 9-28.
- Nurnberger-Haag, J., Kratky, J., & Karpinski, A. C. (2022). The integer test of primary operations: A practical and validated assessment of middle school students' calculations with negative numbers.
- OECD (2022). *Mathematics performance (PISA)*
- Osei, W., & Agyei, D m. D. (2023). Teaching knowledge and difficulties of In-field and Out-of-field Junior High School mathematics teachers in algebra. *Cogent Education*, 10(2), 2232240.
- Osman, S., Yang, C. N. A. C., Abu, M. S., Ismail, N., Jambari, H., & Kumar, J. A. (2018). Enhancing students' mathematical problem-solving skills through bar model visualization technique. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 13(3), 273-279.
- Palisoc Jr., R. F., Ruga, J. J., & Monserrat, N. B. (2019). Improved procedural fluency of the grade 7 students in operation on integers thru mathematics camp learning stations s.y. 2018-2019. 1-12.
- Permata, D., Wijayanti, P., & Masriyah. (2019). Students' misconceptions on the algebraic prerequisites concept: Operation of integer numbers and fractions. *The Sixth Seminar Nasional Pendidikan Matematika Universitas Ahmad Dahlan 2018*. doi:10.1088/1742-6569/1188/1/012059
- PISA 2022: *Mathematics Framework*. (n.d.). <https://pisa-2022-maths.oecd.org/ca/index.html>
- Purwaningrum, J., & Bintoro, H. (2019). Miskonsepsi matematika materi bilangan pada mahasiswa calon guru sekolah dasar. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional MIPA Kolaborasi*, 1(1), 173-180.
- Ralston, N. C., Li, M., & Taylor, C. (2018). The development and initial validation of an assessment of algebraic thinking for students in the elementary grades. *Educational Assessment*, 23(3), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10627197.2018.1483191>
- Rodrigo, D. B., & Alave, A. D. (2021). Academic achievement in algebra of the public high school students in the new normal. *Philippine Social Science Journal*, 4 (3), 65-74. <https://doi.org/10.52006/main.v4i3.381>
- Rohid, N., & Rusmawati, R. D. (2019). Students' Mathematical Communication Skills (MCS) in Solving Mathematics Problems: A Case in Indonesian Context. *Anatolian Journal of Education*, 4(2), 19-30.
- Rosyidah, A. N., Maulyda, M. A., Jiwandono, I. S., Oktaviyanti, I., & Gunawan, G. (2021). Misconceptions and errors integer operations: A study in preservice elementary school teachers (PGSD). *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1779/1/012078
- Salifu, A. S. (2022). The Effects of Balance Model and Algebra Tiles Manipulative in Solving Linear Equations in One Variable. *Contemporary Mathematics and Science Education*, 3(2), ep22012. <https://doi.org/10.30935/conmaths/12028>
- Saligumba, I.P., & Tan, D. (2018). Gradual Release of Responsibility Instructional Model: Its Effects on Students' Mathematics Performance and Self-Efficacy. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*. Volume 7, Issue 8, August 2018.

- Salingay, N., & Tan, D. (2018). Concrete-Pictorial-Abstract Approach on Students' Attitude and Performance In Mathematics, *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, Volume 7, Issue 5, May 2018.
- Segumpan, L., & Tan, D. (2018). Mathematics performance and anxiety of junior high school students in a flipped classroom, *European Journal of Education Studies*, Volume 4, Issue 12.
- Setyawati, R. D., & Indiati, I. (2018). Analysis misconceptions of integers in microteaching Activities. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/1013/1/012146
- Shah, M. N. (2022). Determining the Effect of Bar Model Technique on Students' Mathematical Word Problem Solving Skills. *Journal of Contemporary Teacher Education*, 6, 145-156.
- Siaw, E. S., Shim, G. T. G., Azizan, F. L., & Shaipullah, N. M. (2020). Understanding the Relationship Between Students' Mathematics Anxiety Levels and Mathematics Performances at the Foundation Level. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 10(1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jel.v10n1p47>
- Thomas, L. (2020). Control groups and Treatment groups
- Ünlüer, İ., Kurtuluş, A. (2021). Investigation of conceptual and operational understanding processes of eighth grade students to identities and factorization. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, 12(1), 22-70. <https://doi.org/10.16949/turkbilmat.698535>
- Valencia, A. (2023). The Effects of Structured Game using Algebra Tiles in Learning Multiplication of Binomials.
- WAEC. (2018). Chief Examiners' Report BECE Retrieved from <http://www.waecgh.org/examiners-report>.
- WAEC. (2020). Chief Examiners' Report BECE Retrieved from <http://www.waecgh.org/examiners-report>.
- Waltz, T. (2023). Psychology 105: Research Method in Psychology- Pretest-Posttest Design
- Wilmot, E. M., Yarkwah, C., & Abreh, M. K. (2018). Conceptualizing Teacher knowledge in domain-specific and measurable terms: validation of the expanded Kat framework. *British Journal of Education*, 6(7), 31-48.
- Wingett, A. (2019). Effectiveness of manipulatives within the algebra 1 classroom [unpublished master's thesis]. Goucher College

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